

SCIENTIFIC-THEORETICAL FOUNDATIONS OF ENSURING CONTINUITY AND INTEGRITY ON THE BASIS OF TRANSFORMATION OF THE PROCESS OF TEACHING INFORMATICS AND INFORMATION TECHNOLOGY

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Abstract. Ensuring continuity and continuity on the basis of transformation of the educational process of Informatics and information technology science requires students to prepare for practice through technological tools and programs, develop critical thinking and discussion skills, develop innovative ideas, allow you to set personal study plans, and use new methods and methods. It is also necessary for students to learn how to work cooperatively, which allows them to develop their community experience, exchange ideas and increase creativity. Based on this, this article discusses the basics of ensuring continuity and integrity on the basis of transformation of the process of teaching Informatics and Information Technology.

Keywords: Informatics, Technology, Information, transformation, application, training.

Transforming the process of teaching Informatics and information technology as a pedagogical problem, the main goal of learning is to develop students ' critical thinking, discussion skills, enhance their innovative ideas and make practice important. To solve this problem, strong cooperation is needed between teachers, students and general secondary and professional educational institutions [4, 63-77].

This requires students to prepare for practice through technological tools and programs, develop critical thinking and discussion skills, develop innovative ideas, allow individual study plans to be defined, and use new techniques and techniques. It is also necessary for students to learn how to work cooperatively, which allows them to develop their community experience, exchange ideas and increase creativity [2, 611-612].

The scientific theoretical foundations for ensuring continuity and continuity for the transformation of the process of teaching Informatics and Information Technology Science will be as follows:

1. Students use knowledge in practice: students ' application of theoretical knowledge in practice helps to develop acquired knowledge. This requires that students be prepared for practice through technological tools and programs.
2. Developing students ' critical thinking and discussion skills: students should be taught independent thinking, discussion, and problem solving. This increases their ability to analyze data, understand its importance, and draw conclusions [5].
3. The development of innovative ideas of students: it is necessary to allow students to develop projects aimed at finding innovations, using and mastering new technologies. This increases their creativity and increases interest in technological development.
4. Setting students ' personal study plans: each student's personal requirements, abilities, and documentation must be determined based on the study materials. This allows them to choose their own training style and resources.
5. Methods and methods of teaching: new methods and methods should be used in the teaching of Computer Science and Information Technology. This requires the use of

interactive lessons, tips, projects, online resources, virtual laboratories and other technological tools.

6. Creating student work units: students need to learn to work cooperatively. This allows them to develop their community experience, share ideas, and increase creativity [3, 326-333].

Conclusion. To implement continuity and continuity on a transformational basis the process of teaching Informatics and information technology science, teachers need to teach innovative methods and methods, to create opportunities for students to learn how to use technological tools and programs. It is necessary to teach order and systematic thinking in order to develop the thinking and creative abilities of students. Collaboration and community learning are also important. Schools, higher education institutions and universities must cooperate to ensure scientific research, innovation and development. The importance of ensuring continuity and continuity in the transformation of the process of teaching Informatics and Information Technology Science is significant.

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